
THE SIGNIFICANCE OF PHYSICAL READINESS OF TEENAGE STUDENTS AND THE PROBLEMS OF ITS EVALUATION

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Annotation.

In this article, the annual training hours for assessing the physical fitness of boys are studied in detail. During the year, 10st grade boys analyze the impact of special sports exercises on health and the impact of properly organized sports on the human body, as well as the accumulation of excess weight in the human body . the data obtained as a result of observation were studied .

Key words.

physical exercises, actual body weight, physical activity, muscle tissue, physical training, Broca-Brugsch , tourism.

It is known that our great-grandfather Abu Ali ibn Sina in his brief words about physical exercises often emphasizes that one of the main factors in maintaining health is physical exercise. That's why he systematically prioritized food, sleep, and rest after exercise. In his writings, he also mentioned that by exercising, there is no need for any treatment to get rid of the disease.

Modern experts say that in people who are in good physical shape, regular movement leads to constant deep breathing. This, in turn, sufficiently saturates the muscle tissue in the body with oxygen. As a result, a trained or trained body does not spend extra energy on getting rid of unnecessary fats and unnecessary substances.

In our opinion, without taking into account the presence of certain pathological conditions, various injuries and injuries, as well as the remaining complications arising from them that occur in people involved in physical exercises, putting a load on the body or exercising physical training . in the wrong way can reduce the physical qualities of a young man, adversely affects his formation. Proper preparation of young people and the correct organization of training based on a scientifically based plan is of great importance in protecting their body from various injuries and achieving high results in their chosen sport. At

the same time, the use of the most effective means by those who are involved in achieving the intended goal will give its result.

Taking into account the foregoing, in order to scientifically substantiate the achievement of certain physical qualities that are important in physical training, as well as the achievement of the intended goal as a result of youth activities, gymnastics, athletics, football, sports, games, national movements of people, trips, we consider it appropriate to use such like tourism.

Taking into account the age characteristics of physical fitness, the level of physical fitness of students was assessed. In order to compare the level of physical fitness of students, the results obtained with the help of body mass indicators were analyzed. The Brock-Brugsch index was used to measure body weight .

$(50 + (\text{height, cm} - 150) * 0.75 + \text{age, in years} - 21/4).$

Necessary equipment:

1. Medical scales.
2. Measuring tape.

Results:

If the calculated body weight corresponds to the actual body weight, it is set at 30 points.

For every 1 kg of excess body weight, 5 points are deducted. If the calculated body weight is less than the actual body weight, 5 points are added for each 1 kg.

For example: the actual body weight of student B. Akhmedov is 50 kg. Estimated body weight 49 kg. Akhmedov B received 35 points for the fact that the actual body weight is more than the calculated one.

When examining 21 selected pupils of the 10th grade, 6 out of 21 schoolchildren had the actual body weight corresponding to the calculated body weight. However, it was found that 8 boys from among the selected students regularly went in for sports . In 9 boys, it was found that the body weight is greater than the actual body weight, and in the remaining 6 boys, the body weight is less than the actual body weight. It was found that these students had physical inactivity in their sports history and did not go in for sports. So, in 6 boys - 30 points (normal), in 9 boys - 35-75 points (i.e. above the norm) and in 6 boys - 15-25 points (below the norm) the condition was revealed.

It can be seen that the result of 6 students with normal physical training is normal and they were engaged in properly organized physical activity and sports activities. On the contrary, a low result obtained by 2 students (20, 25 points) indicates that they do less sports or that the loads given as a result of improper

organization of sports training exceed the amount of energy expended. The lowest score (15-20) obtained from the remaining 4 students indicated that they did not go in for sports regularly and, therefore, had low physical fitness.

9 students with high results indicated that they do not play sports at all. Therefore, a low character was evidenced by the low energy consumption of the energy received in nutrition and movement.

It can be said that if we consider the signs and results of physical training about human health, then it is necessary to always support it and develop it at the level of capabilities. At the same time, physical culture is the most important direction. As already mentioned, when doing physical education, the age, gender and physical condition of the participants are taken into account. Based on this, the series, number and methods of performing exercises were determined.

In order to be physically fit, it is always necessary to engage in physical education. It is important for the participant to properly organize the training. Strict observance of the daily routine (time of classes, rest, meals, etc.) is the basis for the correct formation of the student and the achievement of the goal.

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